

SOLAR POWERED AUTOMATIC IRRIGATION BASED ON THE IOTA.Alekhya¹, Dr. S. Kondala Rao², O Ranjith Kumar³

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ranjit.kumar@qiscet.edu.in**ABSTRACT:**

In order to keep their crops green, particularly in the summer, ranchers in the farming industry face a great deal of challenges while dumping water into their fields. They lack a proper understanding of the power accessibility, which is the reason for this. They must wait till the field has been properly irrigated even though it is accessible. They are then asked to stop performing other demonstrations using this technique. But there is a solution—a "solar powered auto irrigation system" to be precise. In the initial stages of a solar-powered irrigation system, PV cells are used to generate electricity, which is then stored in battery-operated batteries. System activity uses the energy that is given by the batteries. It is a water syphon.

I.INTRODUCTION

As we become aware of the fact that the Indian economy is among the most dynamic worldwide. The largest contribution to the Indian economy is made by the horticultural sector. The various designing strategies currently in use need to be upgraded in order to achieve the most extreme use of labour and to obtain the maximum benefit in a particular specified. Consequently keeping up with appropriate measure of water level in the soil is one of the essential prerequisites to collect a decent yield that can be a wellspring of different sorts of supplements whether miniature or full scale for their legitimated development. In the event that we talk about Indian farmers they are most noticeably terrible hit by the starvation that happens because of disappointment of harvests relying on different dry spell factors. Downpour assumes the vital part in choosing the eventual fate of these yields just as the farmers consistently. The over usage of ground water has radically diminished the ground water level in the last 15 years. So it is the need of the hour to use every single drop of water shrewdly with the goal that it can likewise be utilized by our coming age too. Additionally we ought to foster some new techniques that utilize the sustainable wellsprings of energy. The improvement of these new methods will arrive at our objective of practical advancement just as to remove the emanation of ozone-depleting substances to a base level. As the name of our project that is AUTOMATIC IRRIGATION SYSTEM with the assistance of the Solar power is a stage to use some new designing strategies. This procedure will be an awesome choice for the little and medium farmers who endure each year on account of disappointment of yields that occurred each year. The

execution of this innovation has a wide degree in the close by future.

One of the fundamental reasons is the absence of downpours and shortage of land supply water. Extraction of water at customary spans from the earth is decreasing the water level and because of which the zones of un-flooded terrains are continuously expanding. The farmers working in the ranch lands are exclusively subject to the downpours and borewells for irrigation of the land. Regardless of whether the homestead land has a watersiphon, manual mediation by farmers is needed to turn the siphon on/off at whatever point required. Solar energy is the most plentiful wellspring of energy on the planet. Solar power isn't just a solution to the present energy emergency yet in addition an ecological well disposed type of energy. Photovoltaic age is a productive methodology for utilizing the solar energy. Solar boards (a variety of photovoltaic cells) are presently a-days widely utilized for running street lamps, for powering water warmers and to meet home grown burdens. The expense of solar boards has been continually diminishing which energizes its use in different areas. One of the uses of this innovation is utilized in irrigation systems for cultivating. Solar powered irrigation system can be an appropriate option for farmers in recurrent situation with energy emergency in India. This green way for energy creation which gives free energy once an underlying venture is made [2].

II. EXISTING SYSTEM:

A GSM/Bluetooth based remote-controlled integrated irrigation system is part of the current system. Depending on the temperature and humidity readings from the system, the watering time is established. Sensors and type of crop and can automatically irrigate the field when unattended. Information is exchanged between far end and designed system via SMS on GSM network.

A Bluetooth module is also interfaced with the main microcontroller chip which eliminates the SMS charges when the user is within the limited range of few meters to the designated system.

The system informs users about many conditions like status of electricity, dry running motor, increased temperature, water content in soil and smoke via SMS on GSM network or by Bluetooth.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

We are utilizing the ARDUINO UNO, WiFi module, humidity sensor, moisture sensor, temperature sensor, LCD, relay, and water motor in the suggested system. Moisture sensor, rain sensor, solar panel, and water motor are the essential electrical and electronic parts of the proposed system. The moisture sensor measures the soil's relative humidity and turns on the water motor if it is low. If it is raining, the water will be turned off if a rain sensor senses it is coming. Solar energy is converted to electrical energy by a solar panel, which is then stored in a battery. The battery-stored energy will be used to power the water. All sensor status will be shown on an LCD screen and tracked via a website. The status of the soil moisture sensor or an IOT-enabled web page will be used to operate the water motor.

MODULE DESCRIPTION a. ARDUINO UNO:

The company's ATmega328P microcontroller is the basis for the open-source Arduino Uno microcontroller card. The card has advanced and basic info/yield (I/O) pin groups that can be connected to a variety of development cards (safeguard) and circuits. It contains 6 basic I/O sticks,

14 advanced I/O pins (six of which support PWM yield work), and a USB Type B connector that enables Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment) modification. Despite the fact that it can accept voltages between 7 and 20 volts, it can be powered by a USB link or an external 9-volt battery. It is comparable to Leonardo and Arduino Nano. The same Creative Commons Attribution 2.5 licence has been applied to the equipment reference configuration. It's

Fig1: Hardware component Aurdinouno

b. WIFIMODULE:

The ESP8266 WLAN module is a free SOC with a coordinated TCP/IP convention stack, through which each microcontroller can get to your WLAN organization. ESP8266 can have APP or burden another APP processor with using the entire Wi-Fi network's resources. Every ESP8266 module has already been modified. Use AT command Suite firmware to give it access to as many Wi-Fi features as a WiFi screen when plugged into an Arduino device (prepared to use) The ESP8266 module is a valuable circuit board that has a sizable and rapidly expanding local area.

Fig2: Wifi module

c. SOILMOISTURE SENSOR:

The soil moisture sensor is one sort of sensor used to check the volumetric substance of water inside the soil. As the straight gravimetric element of soil moisture needs killing, drying, just as test weighting. These sensors measure the volumetric water content not straight forwardly with the assistance of some different guidelines of soil like dielectric steady, electrical obstruction, in any case

collaboration with neutrons, and substitution of the moisture content.

Fig3: Soil Moisturesensor

d. RAINSENSOR:

A rainsensor is one kind of switching device which is used to detect the rainfall. It works like a switch and the working principle of this sensor is, whenever there is rain, the switch will be normally closed.

Fig3: Rainsensor

III. RESULTS

Fig4:Hardware Implementation

Fig5:Sensors status updated in Webpage

IV. CONCLUSION

The main users of this project are farmers and gardeners who don't have a lot of free time to water their plants and vegetables. Additionally, it includes farmers who misuse irrigation water. The concept can be expanded to include green houses, which rarely utilise manual management. The idea can be expanded to develop entirely automated farms and gardens. If combined with the idea of collecting rainwater, it has the potential to save a lot of water if used properly. This technique can be successfully utilised to get excellent outcomes with most types of soil in agricultural fields with significant rainfall shortages. used to transfer water from an animal well to a tank used to store water. The topic of this article is sun-oriented.

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